

ISic0251

I.Sicily inscription 0251

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 62

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(ecreto) d(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285270

EDR 127489

EDCS 10900673

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 177

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0251. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334759>